

Islamic Work Ethics as a Mediator of the Influence of Compensation, Career Development, Work Environment and Leadership on the Performance of Islamic Bank Employees in Riau Province Reviewed from Islamic Perspectives

Author's Details:

(¹) Nanda Suryadi (²) Yuswar Z Basri (³) Tatik Maryanti (⁴) Zulhelmi

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the Islamic work ethic as a mediator of the influence of compensation, career development, work environment, leadership, on the performance of Islamic bank employees in Riau province reviewed from an Islamic perspective. To be able to compete with other banks, Islamic banking needs to develop human resources who have the skills so that they can be relied upon. This research uses the Structure Equation Model (SEM) by analyzing the facts that have occurred. In this study, primary data were collected using a questionnaire with 288 respondents. The respondents in this study were employees of Islamic Commercial Banks in Riau Province, namely Bank Syariah Mandiri, Bank Muammalat, Bank BNI Syariah, Bank BRI Syariah, Bank BTPN Syariah, Bank BTN Syariah, and Bank Mega Syariah. This study produced some interesting findings including that compensation, career development, work environment, and Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Islamic Bank Employee Performance. Compensation, work environment, and leadership through Islamic Work Ethics have a positive and significant effect on the performance of Islamic Bank Employees in Riau. Career Development through Islamic Work Ethics does not affect the performance of employees of Islamic Banks in Riau. Meanwhile, there are several variables that have an indirect effect on the results of career development through Islamic work ethics that have no effect on employee's performance. The impact of the results of this study, In general, is that performance can be improved by managing the potential of each employee as much as possible. Employees must be given space and opportunities to achieve and perform more optimally. Predicate humans as social beings, so that everyone wants to get attention in work. A friendly climate in the work environment and support each other in doing their work. If those are achieved, the performance of individuals can be further enhanced which will impact the performance of better Islamic bank organizations.

Keywords: Compensation, Career Development, Work Environment, Leadership, Islamic Work Ethic, and Employee Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are important factors in determining the survival of a company because employees are one of the factors of production that play more important role compared to other production factors. Even though a company has complete facilities and infrastructure, without being supported by good, dynamic, disciplined and united human resources, the survival of the company will run slowly and may not last long. Sutrisno (2008)

Banks are financial institutions whose main activities are to collect funds from the public and redistribute the funds to the public and provide other bank services. (Kasmis, 2008). According to Law No. 21 of 2008 concerning Islamic Banking that Islamic banking is everything that concerns Islamic banks and Islamic Business Units covering institutions, activities, and ways and processes in carrying out their business activities.

Islamic banking in Indonesia has experienced very rapid development. Until December 2016 the number of Islamic banks in Indonesia amounted to 199 Islamic banks consisting of 13 Islamic Commercial Banks (BUS), 21 Islamic Business Units (UUS), and 165 Islamic People Financing Banks (BPRS). The following is a complete list of Islamic banks (BUS, UUS, and BPRS) operating in Indonesia until 2016 (data processed from OJK data):

The Indonesian Islamic Bank Association (Asbisindo) estimates that the average human resource requirements (HR) of Islamic banking are around 11,000 per year. Fauzi (2013) said that the growth of the

Islamic banking industry in recent years has driven the high demand for competent human resources. Asbisindo estimates that formal education institutions in Indonesia are only able to supply Islamic economic and financial human resources around 3,750 people per year. In other words, there are still differences in the need for Islamic banking human resources to 7000 people per year.

The fact shows that most of the Islamic bank HR, especially at the middle and upper levels, are dropouts of conventional banks with various motives. It is estimated that 70 percent of Islamic bank employees currently come from conventional banks and non-Islamic educational backgrounds. The lack of human resource skills and cognition in the field of Islamic banking has serious negative impacts, including the implementation of Islamic sharia in banking to be not optimal. As a result, the development of products that truly have a strong Islamic foundation and at the same time have business reliability is hampered. In fact, ideally, the development of this product must be able to bring the community to the nature of businesses that follow sharia, especially in agriculture, trade, investment, and plantations.

Employee performance is important in increasing employee productivity. In improving the performance of employees the company must be able to know the factors that can affect performance. These factors include training and motivation for employees. According to Raymond (2010) to solve problems related to improving employee performance, there are several possibilities that can be done by the company, among others, through providing motivation and job training.

Meanwhile, according to Heidjrachman and Husnan (2010) suggested several factors regarding the needs and desires of employees, namely: good salaries and incentives, safe work, compact co-workers, appreciation for work, meaningful work, opportunity to progress, leaders who fair and wise, reasonable direction and orders, and organizations or workplaces that are valued by the community

According to Swastha and Sukotjo (2011), "Salaries are rewards for services provided regularly and in a certain amount by the company to employees for the contribution of energy that has been given to achieve certain goals. The Effect of Incentives on the performance of Islamic Bank employees is one of the main things that must be considered by the company. The employee's enthusiasm can also be caused by the size of the incentives received.

The better performance of employees will affect one's career development. Career development is an increase in the ability of individual work achieved in order to achieve the desired career. With the development of careers, employees will be rewarded, cared for, needed and recognized by their ability to work by company management so that they will produce high output and will enhance loyalty to the company, namely Islamic banks.

The work environment that focuses on employees can improve employee performance and satisfaction. Conversely, an inadequate work environment will be able to reduce employee performance and ultimately reduce employee motivation.

The Islamic Work Ethic should be applied by an Islamic Bank employee in achieving better performance because every Islamic Bank and financial institution is required to implement Islamic sharia principles, this is certainly different from Non-Sharia companies. The research conducted by (Awais Imam 2013) proves that the Islamic work ethic factor is a good predictor in measuring the performance of Ph.D. faculty employees in Science International Pakistan.

Based on the background of the problem, the research questions can be drawn as follows:

1. What Are the Effects of Compensation on the performance of Islamic Bank employees in Riau?
2. What are the Effects of Career Development on the performance of Islamic Bank employees in Riau?
3. What Are the Effects of the Work Environment on the performance of Islamic Bank employees in Riau?
4. What is the Effect of Leadership on the performance of Islamic Bank employees in Riau?

2. Literature Review

2.1.Tawhidi String Relation Theory (TSR)

According to Choudhury (2002), In Tawhidi String Relations which is a source of knowledge is the Qur'an, where the Qur'an is a holy book/revelation that explains the knowledge of the singularity of Allah, which is called Tauhid.

Al-Qur'an is given to humans so that humans make the order of life in the world by following the behavior of the Prophet Muhammad. According to the epistemology, this is symbolized by (Ω , S). According to the Qur'an, the knowledge is a revelation revealed to humans through suratic processes. Suratic processes are processes that are related to humans and nature. In this system, strong interactions will emerge.

2.2 Salary, Wages and Incentives

Salary for labor are costs that must be incurred by the company and included in costs or product costs. As for a company's decision on salaries, this instrument is very important to provide continuity for the workforce to live so that the performance process in the company can run well.

According to Swastha and Sukotjo (2010), "Salaries are rewards for services provided regularly and in a certain amount by the company to employees for the contribution of energy that has been given to achieve certain goals".

Hasibuan (2001) suggests that incentives are additional remuneration given to certain employees whose achievements are above standard. This incentive is a tool used to support the fair principle in providing compensation.

2.3. Career Development

According to Rivai (2008), career development is the process of improving individual work capabilities achieved in order to achieve the desired career. Mangkunegara and Isyandi (2004) suggest that career development is a staffing activity that helps employees plan their future careers in the company so that the company and employees concerned can develop themselves to the maximum.

Career Development consists of several indicators as follows:

1. Education and training consists of frequency, method, time, and benefits
2. Promotion consists of vertical promotions and horizontal promotions
3. Transfer of employees (transfer) consists of ordinary mutations and promotional transfers

2.4. Leadership

According to Veithzal Rivai (2004), leadership style is a comprehensive pattern of the actions of a leader, both visible and unseen by his subordinates. Leadership style describes a consistent combination of philosophy, skills, traits, and attitudes that underlie one's behavior

While Miftah Thoha (2012) states that leadership style is a norm of behavior used by someone when the person tries to influence the behavior of others as he sees it. So that aligning perceptions among people who will influence behavior with people whose behavior will be influenced become very important position. In Path-Goal Theory developed by Robert House (1971) in Kreitner and Kinicki (2005) states that leadership encourages higher performance by giving activities that influence subordinates to believe that valuable results can be achieved by a serious effort

2.5. Work Environment

However, according to the expert's opinion, the work environment is defined as the overall tooling that is faced, the surrounding environment in which a person works, the method of work, and the work arrangements both as individuals and as a group. Sedarmayanti, (2001) said, "What is meant by the work environment is something that exists in the environment of workers who can influence themselves in carrying out their duties, such as temperature, humidity, ventilation, lighting and noise, cleanliness of the workplace, and whether or not work equipment". Isyandi (2004)

2.6. Islamic Work Ethic

The work ethic of a Muslim is the spirit to walk the straight path, in terms of taking any decision the leaders must hold the mandate, especially the judges. The judge is based on the straight-line ethics as prophet David did when he was asked to decide a fair case and must be based on the values of truth, then make a decision (punish) among us fairly and do not deviate from the truth and point us to the right path. Alkindi, Ali Sumanto (1997).

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Design

This research belongs to the category of explanatory research, namely research that explains the concepts and problems (phenomena) studied to determine the characteristics and relationships between phenomena and variables (causal relationships), then explains the variables that cause the problems studied. Explanatory research aims to explain the interrelationship between research variables through hypothesis testing based on field data. In this study, the relationships between variables, in the form of casual or causal relationships are examined through hypothesis testing.

This research refers to previous research that has been done by According to Harsono (2005), "Salary is the total amount determined as a substitute for services issued by workers". Whereas according to Handoko (2005), "Salary is giving financial payments to employees as remuneration for work carried out and as a motivation for carrying out activities in the future

3.2. Population and Sample

The population taken is all Islamic bank employees in the Riau region totaling 1,026.

The sample used in this study is

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Details

n = sample size

N = Population Size

e = Significance level 0, 05

Based on the formula above, the sample size in this study can be calculated as follows:

$$n = 287.79 \text{ (288) people}$$

3.3 Data Collection Technique

3.3.1. Descriptive Statistics

In this study, descriptive statistics were used as analysis techniques with the aim of explaining or providing demographic information on the respondents' research (gender, level of education, and length of work) and description of the research variables.

This descriptive statistic is used to provide an overview of the respondents' demographics. Descriptive statistics provide a description of a data that is seen from the mean, standard deviation, variance, maximum and minimum, sum, range, kurtosis and skewness (Gozali, 2011)

3.3.2. Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics used in this study apply the Structural Equation Model method based on Partial Least Square (PLS) with the help of Smart PLS 2.0 M3. The selection of the PLS method is based on the consideration that in this study there are constructs formed with reflexive indicators and this study also uses moderating variables. It is known that Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) is a common method used in multiple regressions by entering the third variable which is a multiplication between two independent variables (exogenous) as a moderating variable. This will lead to a non-linear relationship so that measurement errors from the estimated coefficient of MRA if using latent variables become inconsistent and biased, and the solution that can be done is to use structural equation models where SEM can correct these measurement errors by entering interactions into the model.

3.3.3. Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Evaluation of the measurement model or outer model is done to assess the validity and reliability of the model. Outer models with reflexive indicators are evaluated through Convergent Validity and Discriminant Validity from indicators forming latent constructs and Composite Reliability for indicator blocks (Chin, 1998 in Latan and Ghozali 2012).

1. Convergent Validity

Convergent Validity is related to the principle that the measure (manifest variable) of a construct should be highly correlated. Convergent Validity Test of the reflexive indicator with the SmartPLS 2.0 M3 program can be seen from the value of loading factors for each construct indicator

2. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant Validity relates to the principle that different variables (manifest variables) constructs should not be highly correlated. The way to test the Discriminant Validity with a reflexive indicator is by comparing the square root of AVE for each construct with the correlation value between constructs in the model. Good discriminant validity is shown from square root AVE for each construct greater than the correlation between constructs in the model (Fornell and Larcker, 1981 in Latan and Ghozali 2012). The recommended AVE value must be greater than 0.5 which means that 50% or more variance of the indicator can be explained.

3. Composite Reliability

After testing the validity, the measurement of the model is also done to test the reliability of a construct. Reliability testing is done to prove the accuracy, consistency, and accuracy of instruments in measuring constructs. To measure the reliability of a construct with a reflexive indicator carried out with Composite Reliability. The Rule of Thumb commonly used to assess construct reliability, that is, the value of Composite Reliability must be greater than 0.7 for confirmatory assessments and values 0.6-0.7 can still be accepted for exploratory studies (Latan and Ghozali 2012).

4. Evaluation of Structural Models (Inner Model)

In assessing the structural model with PLS, it starts by looking at the R-Squares value for each endogenous latent variable as the predictive power of the structural model. Changes in the R-Squares value can be used to explain the effect of certain exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables whether they have substantive effects. R-Squares values are 0.75, 0.50 and 0.25. It can be concluded that the model is strong, moderate and weak. The results of the PLS R-Squares represent the number of variances of the construct described by the model (Latan and Ghozali 2012).

5. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is done by looking at the significant value to determine the influence between variables. The limit for rejecting or accepting the hypothesis proposed is > 1.67 (significance level = 5%) where if $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ [> 1.67 (one-tailed)], then H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected, but if $t \text{ count} < t \text{ table}$ [< 1.67 (one-tailed)], then H_o is accepted and H_a is rejected. Besides looking at the value of the t tables, to reject or accept the hypothesis must also pay attention to the positive or negative values of the path coefficients.

4. Results and Finding

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

This descriptive statistic is used to provide an overview of the respondents' demographics. Descriptive statistics give a description of a data that is seen from the mean, standard deviation, variance, maximum and minimum, sum, range, kurtosis and skewness (Gozali, 2011).

keterangan	Minimum	Maximun	Mean	Std Deviasi
KOM	20	40	35,33	3,734
PK	16	40	33.5667	4.77084
LK	22	40	35	3.91388
KP	16	40	33.0389	4.94818
EKI	16	40	34.65	4.49516
KIN	16	40	34.2167	4.13228

Source: Processed data

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the minimum value of the variable and the Maximum value, as well as the standard average. This means that the compensation variable is uniform.

4.2. Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Evaluation of the measurement model or outer model is done to assess the validity and reliability of the model. Outer models with reflexive indicators are evaluated through Convergent Validity and Discriminant Validity from indicators forming latent constructs and Composite Reliability for indicator blocks (Chin, 1998 in Latan and Ghazali 2012)

Figure 1 Outer Model

1. Convergent Validity

Convergent Validity is related to the principle that the measure (manifest variable) of a construct should be highly correlated. Convergent Validity Test of the reflexive indicator with the SmartPLS 2.0 M3 program can be seen from the value of loading factors for each construct indicator.

Based on the results of testing the outer loading indicator for compensation, work environment, career development, leadership, Islamic ethics, and engineering variables have a large value of 0.5 so that the individual reflexive size is said to meet the requirements

2. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant Validity Value (Cross Loading)

	Islamic Work Ethic	Leadership	Performance	Compensation	Work environment	Career Development
EKI1	0.851	0.386	0.523	0.419	0.415	0.256
EKI2	0.870	0.306	0.451	0.340	0.283	0.111
EKI3	0.765	0.311	0.510	0.305	0.293	0.199
EKI4	0.814	0.412	0.552	0.429	0.443	0.284
EKI5	0.637	0.381	0.467	0.275	0.278	0.168
EKI6	0.910	0.330	0.519	0.338	0.322	0.179
EKI7	0.841	0.371	0.514	0.417	0.417	0.254
EKI8	0.856	0.334	0.444	0.338	0.283	0.115
KEP1	0.169	0.689	0.275	0.126	0.197	0.308
KEP2	0.437	0.891	0.509	0.434	0.393	0.353
KEP3	0.352	0.770	0.458	0.274	0.351	0.298
KEP4	0.174	0.679	0.287	0.146	0.217	0.323
KEP5	0.424	0.800	0.484	0.422	0.381	0.353
KEP6	0.151	0.682	0.266	0.110	0.189	0.297
KEP7	0.405	0.877	0.480	0.385	0.366	0.359
KEP8	0.361	0.751	0.418	0.275	0.323	0.308
KIN1	0.513	0.441	0.890	0.477	0.530	0.468
KIN2	0.482	0.428	0.813	0.403	0.556	0.492
KIN3	0.566	0.498	0.829	0.541	0.605	0.543
KIN4	0.488	0.436	0.868	0.460	0.497	0.441
KIN5	0.525	0.412	0.869	0.491	0.544	0.492
KIN6	0.438	0.398	0.766	0.321	0.512	0.462
KIN7	0.567	0.488	0.821	0.541	0.589	0.555
KIN8	0.481	0.500	0.837	0.431	0.487	0.443
KOM1	0.357	0.293	0.472	0.862	0.530	0.392
KOM2	0.256	0.230	0.329	0.702	0.343	0.159
KOM3	0.412	0.371	0.505	0.765	0.380	0.361

	Islamic Work Ethic	Leadership	Performance	Compensation	Work environment	Career Development
KOM4	0.356	0.289	0.470	0.859	0.532	0.390
KOM5	0.367	0.264	0.480	0.841	0.542	0.427
KOM6	0.260	0.232	0.335	0.706	0.334	0.155
KOM7	0.298	0.248	0.319	0.686	0.298	0.191
KOM8	0.399	0.456	0.472	0.803	0.385	0.359
LK1	0.370	0.384	0.620	0.432	0.879	0.573
LK2	0.219	0.214	0.394	0.290	0.705	0.365
LK3	0.384	0.449	0.603	0.468	0.870	0.617
LK4	0.313	0.281	0.444	0.475	0.680	0.463
LK5	0.336	0.291	0.429	0.463	0.764	0.439
LK6	0.363	0.313	0.507	0.524	0.823	0.437
LK7	0.395	0.364	0.617	0.445	0.877	0.584
LK8	0.255	0.257	0.413	0.324	0.701	0.414
PK1	0.202	0.372	0.505	0.326	0.584	0.843
PK2	0.196	0.220	0.339	0.243	0.366	0.739
PK3	0.233	0.380	0.510	0.418	0.464	0.708
PK4	0.169	0.375	0.491	0.304	0.560	0.820
PK5	0.165	0.222	0.334	0.218	0.359	0.749
PK6	0.214	0.357	0.494	0.397	0.471	0.669
PK7	0.152	0.331	0.479	0.296	0.577	0.850
PK8	0.151	0.224	0.345	0.222	0.369	0.760

Based on the data above, there are no values for each loading factor for each indicator of the latent variable that has a loading factor that is not the greatest compared to the loading value if it is associated with other latent variables. This means that every latent variable has good discriminant validity where some latent variables do not have a measure that correlates highly with other constructs.

3. Composite Reliability

Cronbach's Alpha Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha (>0.6)	Composite Reliability (>0.7)	Average Extracted (>0.5)	Variance (AVE)
Islamic Work Ethic	0.930	0.943	0.675	
Leadership	0.908	0.921	0.595	
Performance	0.939	0.949	0.701	
Compensation	0.909	0.925	0.610	
Work environment	0.914	0.930	0.626	
Career development	0.902	0.920	0.592	

Source: Processed SmartPLS Data, 2018

Based on the table it can be concluded that all constructs meet reliable criteria. This is indicated by the value of Cronbach's Alphacomposite reliability above 0.70 and AVE above 0.50 as the recommended criteria.

4. Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

Structural Model (Inner Model) dan GoF

Variable	Communality	R Square
Islamic Work Ethic	0.933	0.310
Leadership	0.928	
Performance	0.941	0.644
Compensation	0.919	
Work environment	0.928	
Career development	0.906	
Average	0.926	0.477
GoF	0.441	
	0.664	

Table above shows the value of Goodness of Fit shows a value of $0.664 > 0.36$ GoFLarge. This shows the model in this study matches the data obtained.

5. Hypothesis Testing

Result For Inner Weights

Variable Relationships	Original (O)	sample	Sample Average (M)	Average	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Islamic Work Ethic -> Performance	0.336		0.341		0.084	4.010	0.000
Leadership -> Islamic Work Ethic	0.291		0.290		0.084	3.477	0.001
Leadership -> Performance	0.149		0.146		0.059	2.514	0.012
Compensation -> Islamic Work Ethic	0.244		0.250		0.077	3.167	0.002
Compensation -> Performance	0.124		0.132		0.063	1.986	0.048
Work Environment -> Islamic Work Ethic	0.256		0.255		0.083	3.072	0.002
Work Environment -> Performance	0.218		0.203		0.074	2.929	0.004
Career Development -> Islamic Work Ethic	-0.137		-0.133		0.097	1.417	0.157
Career Development -> Performance	0.253		0.252		0.084	3.009	0.003

Based on the results of the analysis that can be seen in the table, the Islamic Work Ethic path coefficient value

for performance is 0.336 with a calculated t value of 4.010. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant influence of the Islamic work ethic on Performance.

Based on the results of the analysis which can be seen in the table, the Leadership path coefficient value for Islamic work is 0.291 with a calculated t value of 3.477. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant influence of Leadership on Islamic work ethics.

Based on the results of the analysis that can be seen in the table shows the Leadership path coefficient value for the performance of 0.149 with a calculated t value of 2.514. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove a significant influence on leadership on performance.

Based on the results of the analysis that can be seen in the table shows the value of the Compensation path coefficient for Islamic Work Ethics of 0.244 with a value of t count of 3.167. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant influence of Compensation on the Islamic work ethic.

Based on the results of the analysis that can be seen in the table shows the value of the Compensation path coefficient to performance of 0.124 with a value of t count of 1.986. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant effect of Compensation on performance.

Based on the results of the analysis that can be seen in the table shows the path coefficient value of the work environment for Islamic work ethics of 0.256 with a value of t count of 3.072. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant influence of the Work Environment on the Islamic work ethic.

Based on the results of the analysis that can be seen in the table shows the path coefficient value of the Work Environment for the performance of 0.218 with a t value of 2.929. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant influence of the Work Environment on performance.

Based on the results of the analysis that can be seen in the table shows the path coefficient of Career Development towards Islamic work ethics of (0.137) with a value of t count of 1.417. This value is smaller than t table 1.974. These results prove no significant influence on Career Development on the Islamic work ethic.

Based on the results of the analysis that can be seen in the table, the Career Development path coefficient value for performance is 0.253 with at count value of 3.009. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant influence of Career Development on performance.

6. Conclusion

- a. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of Islamic Banks in Riau. Showing the value of the Compensation path coefficient to Performance of 0.124 with a value of t count of 1.986. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant effect of Compensation on Performance.
- b. Career development has a positive and significant effect on Islamic Bank Employees Performance showing Career Development path coefficient value for Performance is 0.253 with a calculated t value of 3.009. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant influence of Career Development on Performance.
- c. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on the Islamic Banks Employee performance. Showing the path coefficient value of the Work Environment against Performance of 0.218 with a value of t count of 2.929. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove a significant influence on the Work Environment on Performance.
- d. Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Islamic Banks Employees Performance. Showing the Leadership path coefficient value for Performance of 0.149 with a calculated t value of 2.514. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove a significant influence on leadership on Performance.
- e. Compensation through Islamic work ethics has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Islamic banks employee in Riau. Showing the value of the Compensation path coefficient of Islamic Work Ethics of 0.244 with a value of t count of 3.167. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant influence of Compensation on the Islamic work ethics.
- f. Career Development through Islamic work ethics does not affect the performance of Islamic Bank employees in Riau. Showing the value of Career Development path coefficient on Islamic Work Ethics

amounting to (0.137) with a calculated t value of 1.417. This value is smaller than t table 1.974. These results prove no significant influence on Career Development on the Islamic work ethics.

- g. The Work Environment through Islamic work ethics has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Islamic Bank employees in Riau. Showing the path coefficient value of the work environment towards Islamic Work Ethics of 0.256 with a value of t count of 3.072. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant influence of Work Environment on the Islamic work ethics.
- h. Leadership through Islamic work ethics has a significant and significant effect on the performance of Islamic Bank employees in Riau. Showing the value of the Leadership path coefficient for the Islamic work ethic of 0.291 with a t value of 3.477. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant influence of leadership on the Islamic work ethics.
- i. Islamic Work Ethics has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Islamic Bank employees in Riau. Showing the Islamic work ethics path coefficient value against Performance equal to 0.336 with a calculated t value of 4.010. This value is greater than t table 1.974. These results prove the significant influence of Islamic work ethics on Performance.

7. Reference

- i. *Alquran Al-Karim*
- ii. *Adiwarman Azwar Karim, . Sejarah Pemikiran Ekonomi Islam. 2004. Jakarta : Raja Grafindo Persada*
- iii. *Abdurrahman Al-Jaziry, Kitab Al-Fiqhu 'Ala Mazahibil Arba`ah, Jilid III, Beirut: Darul-Fikri*
- iv. *Abu Amar, Drs. Imron. Terjemah Fathul Qarib, Menara Kudus, Kudus: 2014*
- v. *Ahmad Warson Munawwir AF, Kamus Al-Munawwir: Indonesia-Arab, Arab-Indonesia, Surabaya: Pustaka Progressif, 1997*
- vi. *Ahsin W. Al-Hafidz, Kamus Ilmu Al-Qur'an, Jakarta: Amzah, 2006*
- vii. *Arakal Salim G.P. Etika Intervensi Negara Perspektif Etika Politik Ibnu Taimiyah (Jakarta 1999)*
- viii. *Ariyoto K. 2001. Feasibility Study, Teknik Evaluasi Usaha Mutiara. Sumber Widya. Jakarta*
- ix. *Azwar, S. "Penyusunan Skala Psikologi", PT. Pustaka Pelajar, 2007.*
- x. *Bambang Setiadji, Upah Antar Buruh Industri di Indonesia, Muhammdiyah University Press, Surakarta, 2002*
- xi. *Busneti, Ida. 2014. Upah menurut sistem Islam dan Sistem Konvensional , Suatu perbandingan Guna mencapai Hidup Layak, Turnover rendah dan Produktivitas tinggi bagi karyawan (Study kasus Restoran di Jabodetabek). Universitas Trisakti Jakarta .*
- xii. *Burgess, S., Ratto, M. (2003), "The role of incentives in the public sector: issues and evidence", Oxford Review of Economic Policy, Vol. 19 No.2, pp.285-9*
- xiii. *Bonner, S.E., Hastie, R., Sprinkle, G.B., Young, S.M. (2000), "A review of the effect of financial incentives on performance in laboratory task: implications for management accounting", Journal of management Accounting Research, Vol. 12 pp.19-64*
- xiv. *Bonner, S.E., Sprinkle, G.B. (2002), "The effects of monetary incentives on effort and task performance: theories, evidence, and a framework for research", Accounting, Organizations and Society, Vol. 27 pp. 303-45*
- xv. *Choyimah. 2005. Dalam skripsi yang berjudul "Pengaruh Pengembangan Pegawai terhadap prestasi kerja pegawai Pada Badan Kepegawaian Daerah Kota Semarang" Pendidikan Ekonomi Fakultas Ilmu Sosial Universitas Negeri Semarang.*
- xvi. *De Brujin, H, (2002), "Performance measurement in the public sector; strategies to cape with the risks of performance measurement", International Journal of Public Sector Management, Vol 15 No 56/7, PP. 578-594*
- xvii. *Defrizal Ridwan. 2002. Dalam skripsi yang berjudul "Upah, Semangat Kerja dan Kepuasan Kerja karyawan pada PT. Medisia Sainsindo*
- xviii. *Desler. Gary . 2006. Manajemen Personalia . Terjemahan Agus Darma. Jakarta : Erlangga.*

- xix. *Evert. Jr. Adam and Ronald J. Ebert, Production and Operation's Management 4th ed ,Prentice Hall, 1989*
- xx. *Filippo, E.B, Manajemen Personalia, Jakarta, Erlangga. Jakarta, 1997*